

Horizon 2020

1. Data Summary

What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

Dataset Katalog Klimadaten Wien:

Dataset Statistik Austria: Energie Ressourcen:

What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?

Dataset Katalog Klimadaten Wien: CSV

Dataset Statistik Austria: Energie Ressourcen: CSV

Will you re-use any existing data and how?

Dataset Katalog Klimadaten Wien: Nachgenutzt

Dataset Statistik Austria: Energie Ressourcen: Nachgenutzt

What is the origin of the data?

Dataset Katalog Klimadaten Wien: Stadt Wien – <https://data.wien.gv.at>

Dataset Statistik Austria: Energie Ressourcen: Statistik Austria <https://www.statistik.at>

What is the expected size of the data?

Dataset Katalog Klimadaten Wien:

Dataset Statistik Austria: Energie Ressourcen:

To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Dataset Katalog Klimadaten Wien: Forscher die den Zusammenhang Klimadaten mit Energie Ressourcen nachvollziehen wollen

Dataset Statistik Austria: Energie Ressourcen:

2. FAIR data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers)?

Dataset Katalog Klimadaten Wien: Nein

Dataset Statistik Austria: Energie Ressourcen: Nein

What naming conventions do you follow?

Dataset Katalog Klimadaten Wien: Nein

Dataset Statistik Austria: Energie Ressourcen:

Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Do you provide clear version numbers?

Dataset Katalog Klimadaten Wien: Die Github Versionierung wird verwendet (Git based VCS).

Dataset Statistik Austria: Energie Ressourcen: Die Github Versionierung wird verwendet (Git based VCS).

What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Dataset Katalog Klimadaten Wien:

- automatic:
- semi-automatic:
- manual:

Dataset Statistik Austria: Energie Ressourcen:

- automatic:
- semi-automatic:
- manual:

2.2. Making data openly accessible

Which data produced and/or used in the project will be made openly available as the default? If certain data sets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from voluntary restrictions.

Dataset Katalog Klimadaten Wien: Ja, extern für alle

Dataset Statistik Austria: Energie Ressourcen: Ja, extern für alle

How will the data be made accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?

Dataset Katalog Klimadaten Wien: Sonstiges: Github

Dataset Statistik Austria: Energie Ressourcen: Sonstiges: Github

What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Dataset Katalog Klimadaten Wien:

Dataset Statistik Austria: Energie Ressourcen:

Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

Dataset Katalog Klimadaten Wien:

Dataset Statistik Austria: Energie Ressourcen:

Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Dataset Katalog Klimadaten Wien: Ja, extern für alle

Dataset Statistik Austria: Energie Ressourcen: Ja, extern für alle

Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited? Preference should be given to certified repositories which support open access where possible.

Dataset Katalog Klimadaten Wien: Sonstiges: Github (not certified)

Dataset Statistik Austria: Energie Ressourcen: Sonstiges: Github (not certified)

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?

Dataset Katalog Klimadaten Wien:

Dataset Statistik Austria: Energie Ressourcen:

Is there a need for a data access committee?

Are there well described conditions for access (i.e. a machine-readable license)?

Dataset Katalog Klimadaten Wien:

Dataset Statistik Austria: Energie Ressourcen:

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

Dataset Katalog Klimadaten Wien: Original Daten sind abrufbar von den Quellen, transformierte Daten werden durch R Skript erzeugt

Dataset Statistik Austria: Energie Ressourcen:

2.3. Making data interoperable

Are the data produced in the project interoperable, that is allowing data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc. (i.e. adhering to standards for formats, as much as possible compliant with available (open) software applications, and in particular facilitating re-combinations with different datasets from different origins)?

Dataset Katalog Klimadaten Wien:

Dataset Statistik Austria: Energie Ressourcen:

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?

Dataset Katalog Klimadaten Wien:

- Es wurde noch nicht entschieden, mit welchem System die Metadaten und Kontextinformationen beschrieben werden

Dataset Statistik Austria: Energie Ressourcen:

Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability?

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies?

Dataset Katalog Klimadaten Wien:

Dataset Statistik Austria: Energie Ressourcen:

2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?

Dataset Katalog Klimadaten Wien: Andere: Creative Commons Namensnennung 4.0 International

Dataset Statistik Austria: Energie Ressourcen: Andere: <http://statcube.at/statistik.at/ext/statcube/jsf/terms.xhtml>

When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

Dataset Katalog Klimadaten Wien: 22. April 2019

Dataset Statistik Austria: Energie Ressourcen: 22. April 2019

Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.

Dataset Katalog Klimadaten Wien: Forscher die den Zusammenhang Klimadaten mit Energie Ressourcen nachvollziehen wollen

Dataset Statistik Austria: Energie Ressourcen:

How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

Dataset Katalog Klimadaten Wien:

Dataset Statistik Austria: Energie Ressourcen:

3. Allocation of resources

What are the costs for making data FAIR in your project?

Personnel:

Other:

How will these be covered? Note that costs related to open access to research data are eligible as part of the Horizon 2020 grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions).

Es gibt keine

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)?

Preservation decisions

Costs

Personnel: 0 PM

Other:

4. Data security

What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)?

Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?

Dataset Katalog Klimadaten Wien: Sonstiges: Github (not certified)

Dataset Statistik Austria: Energie Ressourcen: Sonstiges: Github (not certified)

5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

Dataset Katalog Klimadaten Wien:

Dataset Statistik Austria: Energie Ressourcen:

Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

Dataset Katalog Klimadaten Wien:

- Personal data: Nein
- Informed consent: Es wird keine “informierte Einwilligung” eingeholt

Dataset Statistik Austria: Energie Ressourcen:

- Personal data:
- Informed consent:

6. Other issues

Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?